

SEISMIC RETROFIT OF RC SHORT COLUMNS WITH TEXTILE REINFORCED ALKALI-ACTIVATED OR CEMENT-BASED MORTARS

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ABSTRACT

The effectiveness of textile reinforced mortars (TRM) utilized in a form of jacketing overlays applied on short, shear-critical RC columns is investigated experimentally and verified analytically in this study. Moreover, the possibility of replacing the standard ordinary Portland cement (OPC) matrix with an alternative alkali-activated material (AAM) in the TRM retrofitting technique is explored. A total of seven RC columns were tested, at a scale of approximately 2/3, with the shear span – to – height ratio of 1.5. Four out of seven specimens were designed to be more ductile with closely spaced shear reinforcement, while the rest had their stirrups positioned at larger spacing. Both series of columns were retrofitted with two and four layers of TRM jacket overlays, made of uncoated carbon textile and AAM- or OPC-based mortar, and subjected to cyclic loading combined with a constant vertical load. While control (unretrofitted) specimens exhibited a brittle failure, the retrofitted ones performed significantly better in terms of deformation capacity, with a clear shift of the failure mode towards shear-flexure. The load capacity of jacketed columns was governed by yielding of longitudinal reinforcement. An important result is that AAM-based TRM jacketing is not inferior by any means to its OPC-based counterparts.

This paper was presented at CICE and published (with some differences in the analytical modeling) as follows:

Azdejkovic, L. and Triantafillou, T. (2023). Innovative Retrofitting of RC Structures using Textile-Reinforced Alkali-Activated or Cement-Based Mortar Overlays: Application in Short Columns. In: Ilki, A., Çavunt, D., Çavunt, Y.S. (eds) Building for the Future: Durable, Sustainable, Resilient. fib Symposium 2023. Lecture Notes in Civil Engineering, vol 349. Springer, Cham.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-32519-9_10

KEYWORDS

Alkali-activated materials (AAM), seismic retrofitting, short columns, textile reinforced mortar (TRM).

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.